

Pollution studies of industrial wastes with a reference to toxic trace metals by voltammetry

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The metal pollution status of industrial waste waters in Jodhpur has been examined by monitoring chromium, arsenic, selenium, antimony, lead, cadmium, thallium and mercury concentrations using pulse polarographic and stripping voltammetric methods.

Voltammetric methods may be used under widely differing experimental conditions that is of considerable importance in case of pollution studies¹. As a part of our programme of comprehensive investigations of the nature of pollutants in aquatic environment and their consequential effects on surroundings, the present communication summarizes the results of analysis of industrial effluent of a common *nala* comprising the waste waters of different factories situated in Basni Industrial Area of Jodhpur City. It has enabled the determination of chromium, arsenic, selenium, antimony, lead, cadmium, thallium and mercury using differential pulse polarography (DPP) and anodic stripping voltammetry. However, detailed electrochemical observations have been described elsewhere².

Results and Discussion

DPP and anodic stripping voltammetric studies of Cr^{VI}, As^{III}, Se^{IV}, Sb^{III}, Tl^I, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} were carried out in different media to find out optimum analytical conditions

Table 1 Voltammetric characteristics of toxic metal ions

Metal ion	Supporting electrolyte	Peak potential V	Detection limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
Cr ^{VI}	1 M NaOH	-0.80	0.04
As ^{III}	Oxalate buffer (pH 4.0)	-1.15	0.01
Se ^{IV}	NH ₃ -NH ₄ Cl buffer (pH 8.5)	-1.68	0.005
Sb ^{III}	6 M HCl	-0.25	0.02
Tl ^I	Acetate buffer (pH 4.5)	-0.47	0.05
Pb ^{II}	0.1 M KCl	-0.44	0.001
Cd ^{II}	0.1 M KCl	-0.60	0.001
Hg ^{II}	0.5 M HCl + 0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	+0.19	0.001

for their determination. The interference of some common cations such as Cu, Zn, Mn and Fe was checked at low concentrations. Voltammetric characteristics and the detection limits achieved for these metal ions are included in Table 1.

The pretreated samples were taken into the polarographic cell with appropriate supporting electrolyte and the voltammograms were recorded. Currents were measured at peak potential of the concerned ion after making blank corrections. The concentrations of Cr, As, Se, Sb, Tl, Pb, Cd and Hg were determined in a large number of industrial waste water samples in this manner. The results are summarised in Table 2. Quantitation in all observations was made by standard addition method³

Table 2 Concentration of toxic metal ions in industrial waste water of common *nala*

Metal ion	Concn ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)*			SD (\pm)
	Min	Max	Ave	
Cr	0.049	0.110	0.075	2.6
As	0.023	0.036	0.028	6.2
Se	0.024	0.091	0.054	4.6
Sb	0.052	0.085	0.069	4.5
Tl	ND	ND	-	-
Pb	0.032	0.162	0.084	8.3
Cd	0.001	0.004	0.002	6.0
Hg	0.008	0.013	0.011	3.6

* n = 3, number of determinations

ND = Not detected

Conclusion : Industrial wastes containing chromium, arsenic, antimony, lead, cadmium and mercury raises the risk of affecting the quality of water reserves/resources of this area due to percolation of these hazardous pollutants

through porous soil of land to the underground waters. It is particularly important in the desert and arid regions of western Rajasthan where water shortage is acute problem.

Experimental

A polarographic analyzer (174-A) in conjunction with a drop timer (174/70) and X-Y recorder (RE-0074), all of Princeton Applied Research Corporation, USA were used for voltammetric measurements. The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a dropping mercury electrode was used as the working electrode, modulation amplitude 50 mV, pulse duration 57 ms, clock time of pulse 1 s, and scan rate 5 mV/s. Potentials were recorded against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode throughout. In case of anodic stripping voltammetry, a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) and gold disc electrode (1.6 mm dia of Bioanalytical System, USA) were used for determination of lead and cadmium, and mercury, respectively.

Waste water samples were collected from the selected points of common *nala* in cleaned polyethylene containers. These were filtered to separate particulate matter and also acidified with HCl to pH 2 for storage purposes. Samples

(100 ml aliquot) were treated with an oxidizing mixture of acids to destroy biological materials prior to polarographic estimation. All experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The test solution were deaerated by bubbling with purified nitrogen for 20 min.

Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of the metal ions were prepared from their respective nitrate salts.

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References

1. J. B. Bharathibai and D. K. Padma, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1994, **43**, 10.
2. P. Sharma and R. C. Kapoor, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 51; P. Sharma, *Anal. Sci.*, 1995, **11**, 261; P. Sharma, S. Vyas and S. Sanganeria, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 371; *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1997, **13**, 136; *Int. J. Environ. Anal Chem.*, 1997, **68**, 391.
3. H. Willard, L. Merrit and J. Dean, "Instrumental Methods for Analysis", 5th. ed., Van Nostrand, New York, 1974.